

THE ROLE OF MARKETING ACTIVITIES IN IMPROVING THE AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTION SYSTEM OF NEW UZBEKISTAN

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Orsid code -0009-0000-9577-6976

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20696004>

Abstract. *This article is devoted to the development of marketing services in the agricultural sector, including fruit and vegetable production. The specifics of marketing in the activities of agricultural exporters are shown.*

Keywords: *agriculture, investment, marketing, marketing service.*

Annotatsiya. *Mazkur maqolada qishloq xo'jalik sohasida, jumladan meva-sabzavotlarni ishlab chiqarishda marketing xizmatlarini rivojlantirish masalalariga bag'ishlangan. Qishloq xo'jalik maxsulotlari eksportyorlari faoliyatida marketing hususiyatlari ko'rsatilgan.*

Kalitli so'zlar: *qishloq xo'jalik, investitsiya, marketing, marketing xizmati.*

Аннотация. *Данная статья посвящена вопросам развития маркетинговых услуг в сельском хозяйстве, в частности производстве плодоовощной продукции. Показаны особенности маркетинга в деятельности экспортёров сельскохозяйственной продукции.*

Ключевые слова: *сельское хозяйство, инвестиция, маркетинг, служба маркетинга.*

Introduction. Today, in our Republic, comprehensive measures are being implemented at an accelerated pace to expand production, storage, processing and export of fruit and vegetable products. To implement projects for the intensive development of fruit and vegetable growing, arable land has been significantly expanded, additional capacities for the storage and processing of fruit and vegetable products have been launched, and financial resources, including funds from international financial institutions, are being actively attracted. For example, in January-December 2019, 8% of investments worth 189,924.3 billion soums were directed to the agricultural sector. As a result, the volume of agricultural products produced this year amounted to 215.7 trillion soums, or 102.7% compared to 2018, including agricultural products - 108.3 trillion soums (103.7%), livestock products - 107.4 trillion soums (101.7%).

Analysis of literature on the topic. An analysis of the existing literature on marketing shows the need to improve modern marketing principles, brand promotion methods and a flexible approach to consumer requirements. In his textbook on marketing strategies, the expert RGIbragimov states the following: "Marketing strategy is understood as the use of a model of the principles of the enterprise's behavior in the market, established for a certain period of time. With its help, the enterprise seeks to ensure its success." Many economists have been involved in the development and implementation of marketing strategies. Among them are such famous scientists as F. Kotler, David Aaker, Clayton Christensen, Seth Godin, Kevin Keller, Byron Sharp, and Jay Bayer.

While the research in the field of marketing conducted in our country for many years is based on national characteristics, it is also necessary to recognize the scientists who have made a significant contribution to the development of marketing theory. These include R.Ibragimov, YO.Abdullaev, A.Saliev, M.Sharifkhodjaev, D.Rakhimova, Sh.Ergashkhodjaeva, Sh.Musayeva and others.

Research methodology.The study used a systematic approach, marketing analysis, benchmarking, and digital metrics. Mass surveillance methods were used to collect and analyze data from social media platforms.

Analysis and results.The issue of strengthening reforms in the agro-industrial complex remains urgent for our country. The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan"March 14, 2019""On measures to develop agricultural cooperation in the field of fruit and vegetable growing"№. PQ-4239In the decisionThe goal is to encourage the creation of a value-added chain in the fruit and vegetable sector, ensure the production and sustainability of quality fruit and vegetable products, expand the financial capabilities of producers of these products, and increase the competitiveness of production..

At the same time, the high level of competition in foreign fruit and vegetable markets requires the rapid introduction of modern methods of agricultural technology and management of production and product supply processes.

The use of advanced technologies for growing products in the sustainable development of fruit and vegetable growing, the introduction of modern methods of processing and storing products, makes it possible to prevent food shortages today. As is known, the grown fruit and vegetable products undergo a number of technological processes before reaching the consumer in the form of a finished product. Not only to prevent the destruction of fruits and vegetables, but also to expand the cultivated areas and increase the gross yield, pose great challenges for specialists in this field. For this, first of all, great attention should be paid to the selection of varieties to be planted and agrotechnical processing processes. Harvesting fruits and vegetables in a timely manner as they ripen and transporting them to the necessary subsequent stages in a timely manner will give good results.

International experience shows that achieving competitiveness and entering world markets can be achieved primarily through consistent economic reform, deepening structural transformation and diversification, ensuring the rapid development of new enterprises and production sectors based on high technologies, modernization of existing capacities, and effective use of marketing technologies.

International experience shows that taking into account controllable internal factors, including product, price, location, and market penetration, determines marketing effectiveness. However, many fruit and vegetable producers do not control these factors when organizing marketing management. Having become acquainted with their concepts and approaches, it can be concluded that they do not have a clearly developed strategy for interacting with producers to bring their products to the final consumer.

In many cases, the organization of marketing activities is limited to purchasing, storage, and transportation, but not so much attention is paid to the distribution of the product, that is, its sale. As is known, the distribution of produced fruit and vegetable products and the purchase of raw materials are the decisive factors in the development of the industry, and it is these factors that should be the basis of the enterprise's marketing strategy.

The above-mentioned resolution of the President of our country instructed exporters of fruit

and vegetable products to "approve the procedure for providing subsidies to cover 50 percent of the costs associated with conducting marketing research on foreign markets for fruit and vegetable products produced by members of agricultural associations."

In the organization of fruit and vegetable marketing in countries with developed market economies, it can be seen that commodity producers quickly and accurately identify changes in consumer demand and take appropriate measures. Therefore, for marketing to be successful, enterprise managers must clearly define tasks and make decisions based on accurate information about their current material and financial situation.

In conclusion, the current state of fruit and vegetable marketing should force enterprise managers to find answers to the following questions in order to assess their position in the domestic and foreign markets and, ultimately, determine a strategy for organizing marketing work:

- how the enterprise is operating, that is, whether it is necessary to analyze the current state of the enterprise or not;
- why the enterprise occupies the low-price segment of the market in which it sells its products;
- what needs to be done to improve product quality in order to increase profits;
- how is the development of the enterprise planned - is technical and financial information from domestic and foreign fruit and vegetable markets being used?
- Is a business plan drawn up for each product to be released and is this plan analyzed throughout the chain of delivery of the product to the consumer?

In many companies in the industry, marketing responsibilities are assigned to specific departments, which is completely wrong. Companies should view the marketing concept as a business philosophy that requires the support of all employees and personnel of the company. Viewing marketing as a development concept allows the company to achieve its goals in terms of satisfying the needs of not only consumers, but also society as a whole.

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